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Experimental Physics

Photoemission and Low Energy Electron Diffraction in Solids

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Abstract

ARPES (Angle-Resolved Photoelectron Spectroscopy), and LEED (Low Energy Electron Diffraction) can be realized as significant surface science techniques which provide insights into the fundamental properties of materials and their behavior at the atomic and electronic scales. ARPES can be recognized as an electronic structure characterization technique, whereas LEED is a structural characterization technique. In this experiment, we studied these two techniques with selected materials (Au and InSe) and achieved insightful and interesting observations and results.

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1 Experiment 01: Photo emission in Solids (ARPES)

1.1 Introduction of photoemission and ARPES

The German physicist Heinrich Rudolf Hertz first observed and worked on the photoelectric effect in 1887. He found that the maximum kinetic energy of photoelectrons is independent of the light intensity but proportional to the frequency of the incident light. Later in 1905, by invoking the quantum nature of light, Albert Einstein recognized that when light is incident on a sample an electron can absorb a photon and escape from the material with kinetic energy. This is represented in Equation 1, where E_k is the kinetic energy of the emitted electron, h represents the Planck's constant, ν is the frequency, and ϕ represents the work function of the metal.

$$E_k = h\nu - \Phi \tag{1}$$

Figure 1: This figure shows the schematic diagram of an early “photoemission” experiment. Image source: [1]

The simplest model of ARPES is the three-step model, which separates the process into photon absorption, electron transport through the sample, and emission through the

surface. In the first step, the incident photon with energy $h\nu$ is absorbed by an electron in an initial occupied state, causing it to be promoted to an unoccupied final state. The conservation of energy of this situation is explained in Equation 2, where E_B is the binding energy of the electron.

$$h\nu = E_B + \Phi + E_{\text{kin}} \quad (2)$$

In principle, Photo Emission (PE) is performed today in the same way as it was almost a hundred years ago. The light source is either a gas-discharge lamp, an X-ray tube, or a synchrotron-radiation source instead of a monochromator like before.

Figure 2: (a) Relation between the energy levels in a solid and the electron energy distribution produced by photons of energy $h\nu$. (b) The Angle-Resolved Photoemission Spectroscopy. Image source: [2].

The kinetic energy of the electrons is measured by an electron energy analyzer. If the number of emitted electrons is then plotted as a function of their kinetic energy, as shown in Figure 1, peaks are found whenever an allowed transition takes place. Equation 1 then yields the kinetic energy of the electron if the work function is known. Measuring ϕ

accurately is not a trivial task, but fortunately, in the case of a metallic sample one does not need to know ϕ . By placing the sample in electrical contact with a good metal (such as poly-crystalline gold) one can measure the binding energy in the sample with respect to the chemical potential (Fermi level E_f) of Au.

The photoemission signal from Au will simply be a Fermi function convolved with the experimental energy resolution, and from the midpoint of its leading edge, one estimates E_f .

The existence of the sample surface breaks (discrete) translational invariance in the direction normal to the surface. However, two-dimensional translational invariance in the directions parallel to the surface is still preserved, and thus $k_{||}$ the component of the electron momentum parallel to the surface, is conserved in the emission processes. It is given by Equation 3, where $k_{||}$ is the parallel k vector, m is the mass of the emitted electron, and θ represents the angle between the the emitted electron and the hypothetical normal drawn to the surface.

$$\hbar k_{||} = \sqrt{(2mE_{kin})} \sin \theta \quad (3)$$

The light source is either a gas-discharge lamp, an X-ray tube, or a synchrotron radiation source. The light impinges on the sample, which is a gas or the surface of a solid, and the electrons excited by the photoelectric effect are then analyzed with respect to their kinetic energy E_{kin} and their momentum p in an electrostatic analyzer. The polarization of the light is a useful property in an angle-resolved PE experiment. The important parameters to be measured are then the kinetic energy E_{kin} of the photoemitted electron, and its angle with respect to the impinging light and the surface.

1.2 ARPES: A surface-sensitive technique

The probing depth of ARPES is limited to a few nanometers, comparable to the distance between the atoms in a metal (\AA). Also due to the fact that the mean free path of electrons is very short (also in \AA) and it depends on the kinetic energy of the electrons and not the chemical nature of the material.

The solid sample has core levels and a valence band. In the present case of a metal, the Fermi energy E_f is at the top of the valence band and has a separation ϕ from the vacuum level E_{vac} . If photo absorption takes place in a core level with binding energy E_B ($E_B = 0$ at E_f), the photo-electrons can be detected with kinetic energy as indicated in Equation 4.

$$E_{\text{kin}} = h\nu - \Phi - |E_B| \quad (4)$$

If the energy distribution of the emitted electrons is plotted, their number per energy interval often gives a replica of the electron-energy distribution in the solid. This is an attractive feature of PES; it is able to provide us with information on the electron energy distribution in a material.

1.3 Sample Preparation

1.3.1 For the case of a metal (Au)

A 3nm layer of amorphous gold deposited on Molybdenum is taken as the sample. Due to its low reactivity to Oxygen Au is a good choice. It is welded onto a copper holder to keep it in position and placed inside the Ultra High Vacuum (UHV) vessel. This is presented in Figure 3 (a).

Figure 3: (a) Gold sample on graphite holder (b) InSe sample on copper holder

1.3.2 For the case of a semiconductor (InSe)

Due to the presence of 2D layers, there is high contamination from atmosphere exposure. We could remove the impurities along with the top layer using a sticky surface like scotch tape. Here we attach a ceramic to the semiconductor material using resin which is knocked off after the sample is placed inside the chamber, removing the impurities with it. This is presented in Figure 3 (b).

1.4 Experimental Apparatus

The apparatus consists of a monochromatic light source, vacuum chamber, pumps, sample manipulator, electrostatic lenses, detector, and analyzer (See Figure 4).

Need for UHV:

In the kinetic energy range of interest between about 10 and 2000 eV, the “universal” electron mean free path λ in \AA as a function of the electron kinetic energy for a few selected metals. This means that any spectroscopy of a solid surface involves electrons

Figure 4: This figure shows the basic components of the experimental apparatus. (a) PES Experimental setup (b) Sample manipulator (c) Sample placed inside the vacuum chamber (d) Helium discharge lamp – UV photon source

from a very thin layer of the sample. Hence to learn about the bulk properties of the solid one has to work with automatically clean surfaces. But also, the investigation of surface states or adsorbed molecules requires UHV conditions to prevent interference from

adsorbed contaminants. Hence a low pressure of about 10^{-9} mBar is applied inside the chamber to keep the electrons from scattering.

Photon source:

The light source is a Helium discharge lamp. When passed through an electric current excited Helium atom emit UV radiation of energy 21.2 eV. The photons from the lamp hit the surface of Au. The work function (i.e. the amount of energy required to remove an electron from the metal) of Au is 5.10 eV. Hence an electron of Kinetic energy around 16.1 eV is expected to have been emitted from the metal upon irradiation by this UV light.

1.5 Density of states (DOS)

The density of states, $g(E)$, describes the number of quantum states available in the bath within an energy range from E to $E + dE$. Figure 5 shows the three-dimensional \vec{k} space.

Figure 5: This figure shows the three-dimensional K-sphere. Image source: [3]

In simple metals the DOS can be calculated for most of the energy band, using Equation 5, where E is the energy of the bath, and m^* is the effective electron mass.

$$g(E) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2} \left(\frac{2m^*}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} E^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

However, when we reach energies near the top of the band, we must use a slightly different equation. To derive this equation, we can consider that the next band is separated from the first band by an energy gap of E_g eV.

The energy of this second band ($E_2(k)$) is given in Equation 6.

$$E_2(k) = E_g - \left(\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m^*} \right) \quad (6)$$

From this, we can derive the DOS for the case when there is an energy gap as displayed in Equation 7.

$$g(E) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2} \left(\frac{2|m^*|}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (7)$$

1.6 Fermi-Dirac Distribution

A Fermi sphere is defined by the number of states in \vec{k} space necessary to hold all the electrons needed to add up the average energy of the crystal which is known as the Fermi energy.

The Fermi Dirac distribution applies to fermions, the particles with a half-integer spin, that obey the Pauli exclusion principle. It gives the probability of a state at energy ε being occupied f_{FD} as indicated in Equation 8, where ε is the energy, μ represents the chemical potential, k is the Boltzmann coefficient, and T represents the temperature.

$$f_{FD}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{\varepsilon - \mu}{kT}\right)} \quad (8)$$

1.7 Chemical Potential

The rate of change of free energy in the species with respect to the number of atoms or molecules of the species that are added to the system is called the chemical potential.

Figure 6: This figure shows the obtained probability distribution function against the energy. After first approximating the function to be a Fermi-Dirac function, it was convoluted with two other linear functions to get the best fit (shown in Equation 9). The obtained values for variables are also presented.

In the context of the metal under study, the chemical potential at 0K is given by the Fermi energy.

First, The observed energy values were fitted to a general Fermi-Dirac function, and then the basic function was altered to get the best fit to represent the recorded data as shown in Equation 9.

$$f(E) = (E \times \text{slope} + \text{yintercept}) \times \left(\text{base} + \frac{\text{max}}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{x_{\text{half}} - E}{\text{rate}}\right)} \right) \times (E \times \text{slope2} + \text{yintercept2}) \quad (9)$$

The arbitrary values in Equation 9 were determined using the curve fitting method, and the determined values are presented in Figure 6.

The value for $K_B T$ was determined as $(0.029 \pm 0.001)eV$ (as shown in Figure 6), with a slight deviation to the theoretical value which is 0.025 eV.

1.8 ARPES study on a semiconductor

The material under study is Indium Selenide. It is a layered semiconductor. It has two-dimensional layers bonded together by Vander-Waals's force. The surface of the material is irradiated with the UV source like before to obtain the spectra.

The ARPES spectra obtained from the study of InSe are presented in Figure 7. We can visualize the different valence bands shown in red and the energy gap above it in black.

1.9 Effective mass of the electron

The mass of an electron in the periodic potentials of a crystal is different from the free electron mass and is usually referred to as the effective mass. From the spectra, the maximum kinetic energies are noted for varying k vectors and plotted to fit a parabola. The coefficient of the equation gives the factor that decides the effective mass of the electron inside the material. We can observe from here that the electrons inside the semiconductor are about 1.36 times heavier than the regular electrons.

Then the equation of the parabola (obtained using the fitted curve) was equated to Equation 10.

Figure 7: This figure represents the ARPES spectra obtained from the study of InSe.

$$E(k) = E_B + \left(\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m^*} \right) \quad (10)$$

The Binding energy of InSe was obtained as 1.36 eV. Then by equating the slope of the fitted curve to the coefficient of k^2 (a in the quadratic equation in Figure 8), Equation 11 is obtained (considering the modulus value).

$$a = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \quad (11)$$

Then the reduced mass of the electron can be derived as shown in Equation 12.

$$m^* = \frac{\hbar^2}{2a} \quad (12)$$

Figure 8: This figure shows the behavior of the energy values against the K vector. The observed data were fitted with a quadratic polynomial function $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ (shown in red), with $a = -3.2262$, $b = 0.1709$, and $c = -1.3661$.

Substituting values for \hbar and $a = -3.22$ (obtained using the fitted curve), the following expression shown in Equation 13 is acquired, where m_e is the mass of the electron.

$$m^* \cong 1.2m_e \tag{13}$$

We can observe from here that the electrons inside the semiconductor are about 1.2 times heavier than the regular electrons.

2 Experiment 02: Low-Energy Electron Diffraction (LEED) in solids

2.1 Principles and interests of LEED

Low energy electron diffraction can be recognized as a technique used in solid-state physics to conduct studies in the surface structure of the materials at an atomic level. In this technique, the low-energy electrons are scattered off a surface, and then generated diffraction patterns are analyzed. With the aid of the diffraction patterns, the arrangement of atoms on the surface of the material, the symmetry of the surface, and its periodicity can be determined.

The arrangement of the atoms on the surface corresponds to the above-mentioned diffraction patterns. The electrons tend to interact with the atoms on the surface of the material when a beam of low-energy electrons is shed upon it. As a result, the electrons get scattered. In this technique, the electron beam has lower energies (usually around 100eV), and its comparatively lower than the energies of the beams used in other diffraction patterns such as X-ray diffraction.

In LEED, a vacuum chamber is used to secure the sample to be studied. Then a cathode is used to produce a beam of low-energy electrons. Then the beam is directed through an optical arrangement at the surface of the sample and an electron detector is used to collect the scattered electrons. Inside the detector using a filter method, an avalanche effect is created for the electrons. This detector is capable of measuring not only the intensity but also the angle of diffracted electrons that are used to construct the diffraction pattern in the next step.

LEED is highly successful in studying surfaces that are unstable and reactive because the other commonly used techniques are not capable of analyzing those. Another important fact is that LEED is capable of studying surfaces under different temperatures and pressures,

which gives the opportunity to study the behavior of the material under different conditions.

The applications of LEED are found in various fields such as solid-state physics, material science, and chemistry. The ability to only study surfaces that are periodic and flat can be recognized as a major limit in this technique. As a result, it is not appropriate to study surfaces that have complex structures and that are not periodic.

2.2 Diffraction and Bragg's law

The behavior of waves that tend to bend or scatter as they pass through an obstacle is known as diffraction. The size of the obstacle or the aperture relative to the wavelength of the waves corresponds to the degree of diffraction. This phenomenon is fundamental and takes place in light, sound, and electrons.

Bragg's law can be realized as a fundamental principle in the field of crystallography, and it explains the conditions under which the diffraction of waves takes place. According to the law, when a wave finds a periodic arrangement of atoms or molecules that are spaced by the interplanar distance, diffraction occurs. The angle at which the incident wave is diffracted is known as the diffraction angle and it is correspondent to the interplanar distance and the wavelength of the waves.

The mathematical expression of Bragg's law is given as in Equation 14, where d is the interplanar spacing, θ is the diffraction angle, n is an integer (called the order of diffraction), and λ is the wavelength of the waves.

$$2d\sin\theta = n\lambda \tag{14}$$

2.3 Low-energy electrons are well-suited to study the surface of materials

The main advantages of using low-energy electrons to study the surface of materials can be listed as follows.

Non-destructivity: The low-energy electrons are capable of interacting with the atoms of the surface of the sample without causing significant damage to it (the time duration of the experiment could be an important factor here). As a result, we can study the materials without changing their properties which can be helpful to obtain better results in studies.

Higher resolution: The electron beam used in LEED is capable of creating high-resolution images since they have low energies. As a result, we can study material surfaces in great detail.

Surface sensitivity: The properties of the material are often influenced by the surface atoms and the first few layers under the surface. Since the low energy electrons can only penetrate a few layers inside the material, it can provide a greater amount of details about the properties of the material.

Versatility of usage: Due to the usage of lower energies, we can study a wide range of materials such as metals, semiconductors, insulators, and alloys. Additionally, it helps to study under different conditions such as different pressures and different temperatures.

2.4 Experimental Apparatus

The experimental apparatus used for LEED (low energy electron diffraction) typically consists of the following components (shown in Figure 9):

Vacuum chamber: A vacuum chamber is used to create a high vacuum environment in which the LEED experiment is performed. This is necessary because the electrons used in LEED have low energies, and they can be easily scattered by any gas molecules present

in the chamber.

Electron gun: An electron gun is used to produce a beam of low-energy electrons. The electron gun typically consists of a cathode, which produces the electrons, and an anode, which accelerates the electrons to the desired energy.

Sample holder: The sample to be studied is placed in a sample holder, which is usually mounted on a goniometer. The goniometer allows the sample to be rotated and positioned at different angles relative to the incident electron beam.

Electron detector: An electron detector is used to measure the intensity and angle of the diffracted electrons. The detector can be a scintillation counter, a proportional counter, or a multi-channel plate detector, depending on the specific requirements of the experiment.

Data acquisition system: A data acquisition system is used to collect and process the data from the electron detector. The data acquisition system typically includes a computer, software for analyzing the data, and a data storage system.

2.5 The material under study.

The studied material was Indium(II) selenide, also known as indium monoselenide, which is a chemical compound with the formula InSe . Indium is a metallic element that belongs to group 13 of the periodic table, and selenium is a non-metallic element that belongs to group 16. Indium(II) selenide is a black solid that is relatively stable in air and is resistant to water. It has a high melting point of $1035\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a boiling point of $1750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. It is a direct bandgap semiconductor, which means that it has a small energy gap between the valence band and the conduction band. This makes it an attractive material for use in electronic devices such as solar cells, transistors, and infrared detectors.

As shown in Figure 10, Indium selenide has a hexagonal crystal structure (two-dimensionally), in which the atoms are arranged in a hexagonal pattern. This type of crystal structure is common in materials such as graphene, graphite, and certain types of metals and alloys.

Figure 9: This figure shows different components of the experimental apparatus used in LEED. (a): The vacuum chamber, (b) The electron gun, (c) The sample holder and the detector, (d) The data acquisition system with the PC for observing the spectrum. This is discussed in section "[Experimental Apparatus](#)")

The hexagonal crystal structure is also characterized by its unit cell, which is the smallest repeating unit of the crystal. In a hexagonal crystal structure, the unit cell is a hexagonal prism, which is a six-sided prism with hexagonal bases. The unit cell is used to describe the

atomic arrangement in the crystal and to determine the overall symmetry of the crystal.

Figure 10: This figure shows the crystal structure of InSe. The hexagonal structure is visible where the atoms are arranged in a hexagonal pattern. The purple dots represent the In atoms and the yellow dots are Se atoms. Image Source: [4]

2.6 The LEED patterns obtained on the material

Figure 11 shows the different LEED diffraction patterns obtained on the material. The diffraction pattern consisted of a series of bright spots on a dark background that correspond to the positions of the diffraction maxima. The position, intensity, and shape of the bright spots are related to the surface structure of the sample, and the wavelength of the incident electrons. We observed that the diffraction pattern and the direct lattice have the same hexagonal crystal structure (will be discussed in section "The correlation between the symmetry of the diffraction pattern and the crystal symmetry").

We started the experiment with an electron beam having an energy of 81.6 eV shown in 11(c). Then Subfigure 11(b) represents the diffraction pattern observed for an electron beam of 78.4 eV which is in the same order as the previous one. Therefore, no noticeable difference was observed between the two. We could observe more than two Brillouin zones for the two cases.

However, when we decrease the primary electron energy, the resolution was decreased since energy E and θ have an inversely proportional relationship as shown in Equation 16

(will be discussed in section ["Changing the primary electron energy"](#)). As a result, we could only observe more or less a single Brillouin zone. This behavior (displayed in Subfigure [11\(a\)](#)) could be mathematically explained as displayed in Equation [16](#), which was derived using Equation [14](#) and Equation [15](#).

Then we started increasing the energy of the electron beam and observed that at 88 eV, only three nodes of the hexagonal structure produced bright spots. Then at 104 eV, the other three nodes produced bright spots in the diffraction pattern. We know that InSe is a hexagonal crystal structure (shown in Figure [10](#)) and the In atoms and Se atoms have two different structure factors. This factor is important here because it describes the interference between the diffused waves by the atoms of the basis of the crystal structure. Depending on the type of interference (constructive or destructive), the diffracted intensity can be increased or even become null. This is the situation observed in Figure [11\(d\)](#) and [11\(e\)](#).

Figure [11\(f\)](#) shows the diffraction pattern obtained with an electron beam with 115.2 eV. As predicted in Equation [16](#), the resolution has been increased, and we could observe a couple of more Brillouin zones in the LEED pattern. It was also noted that the intensity of the bright spots has been increased (will be discussed in section ["Changing the primary electron energy"](#)).

$$\lambda[nm] = \frac{0.12}{\sqrt{E[eV]}} \quad (15)$$

$$\sqrt{E} \propto \frac{1}{\lambda} \propto \frac{1}{\sin\theta} \propto \frac{1}{\theta} \quad (16)$$

2.7 The correlation between the symmetry of the diffraction pattern and the crystal symmetry

The symmetry of the diffraction patterns directly corresponds with the crystal symmetry of the material that is under study. Generally, the crystal structure and the diffraction pattern have the same symmetry. The symmetry elements and symmetry operations describe the symmetry of the crystal structure. Rotational axes, mirror planes, and inversion centers can be regarded as examples of symmetry elements.

The arrangement of the atoms in a given crystal structure determines the symmetry of the diffraction pattern. There is a one-to-one correspondence between the two subjects as shown in Figure 11. In the crystal structure of the InSe sample, the atoms in this lattice are arranged in a way that the crystal has a six-fold rotational symmetry. This means that the crystal looks the same when rotated by 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, or 360 degrees around its center. We saw similar behavior in the diffraction patterns as well.

In addition to rotational symmetry, the hexagonal crystal structure also has a mirror plane of symmetry. This means that if the crystal is divided along a plane, the atoms on one side of the plane are a mirror image of the atoms on the other side. The diffraction pattern exhibited the same behavior as shown in Figure 11.

2.8 Changing the primary electron energy

In the LEED experiment, the energy of the incident electrons is comprehended as the primary electron energy. Changing the primary electron energy can have a significant effect on the diffraction pattern obtained in the experiment.

Generally, increasing the primary electron energy will decrease the wavelength of the incident electrons and increase the resolution of the diffraction pattern, because the energy E and the diffraction angle θ have an inversely proportional relationship as shown in Equation 16. Otherwise, when we decrease the energy of the electron beam, the resolution of

the diffraction pattern decreases. This was also discussed in section ["The LEED patterns obtained on the material"](#), using Equation 16.

Changing the primary electron energy can also impact the intensity of the diffraction pattern. In general, increasing the primary electron energy will increase the intensity of the diffraction pattern, while decreasing the primary electron energy will decrease the intensity of the diffraction pattern. This too was observed (see Figure 11) during the experiment.

2.9 Rotating the sample azimuthally

In the LEED experiment, there are two ways that we can rotate the sample; azimuthally and polarly. When we rotate the sample azimuthally, the diffraction patterns also rotate around the node (000). This was also observed in the experiment. When we rotate the sample polarly, the diffraction pattern gets shifted.

Figure 11: This figure shows the different diffraction patterns obtained on the material with electron beams with different energies, (a) 51.2 eV, (b) 78.4 eV, (c) 81.6 eV, (d) 88 eV, (e) 104 eV, (f) 115.2 eV. This is discussed in section ["The LEED patterns obtained on the material"](#))

3 Conclusions

ARPES, to be put simply, is a photon-in electron-out technique that helps us to study and map the band structures and energy gaps of metals and semiconductors. Operating in such a high vacuum has helped us gain an insight into the prerequisites of performing experiments at extreme conditions also helping us investigate the electronic structure of materials.

Au and InSe were the two materials used in this study. For Au, the probability distribution function (in terms of energy) was plotted against the observed energies using ARPES. After first approximating the function to be a Fermi-Dirac function, it was convoluted with two other linear functions to get the best fit for the recorded data. The value for $K_B T$ was determined as $(0.029 \pm 0.001)eV$, with a slight deviation to the theoretical value which is 0.025 eV.

InSe was used as a semiconductor material and the different valence bands and energy gaps were observed using the obtained spectra. From the obtained spectra, the maximum kinetic energies were recorded for varying k vectors and plotted to fit a parabola, for which we used to investigate the effective electron mass. We calculated that the electrons inside the semiconductor are approximately 1.2 times heavier than the regular electrons.

Low Energy Electron Diffraction (LEED) was investigated as a technique based on the scattering of low-energy electrons by the surface atoms to study the arrangement of atoms at the surface of a crystal, with a higher resolution and a higher sensitivity.

InSe was the material used in this study that has a hexagonal crystal structure and later we observed that the diffraction pattern and the direct lattice share the same crystal structure. Furthermore, a strong correlation between the symmetry of the diffraction pattern and crystal symmetry was also observed.

The effect of changing the primary electron energy was investigated in the experiment and we observed that the resolution and the intensity of the diffraction pattern are highly

affected. Additionally, we followed that by rotating the sample (azimuthally or polarly), so we could get interesting and insightful physical observations.

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